

Replication Studies Call for proposals

2025

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1 Introduction

In this Call for proposals information is provided about the application procedure for the “Replication Studies 2025” funding round. This Call for proposals falls under the responsibility of Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council (NWO).

In this Call for proposals, you will find information about the aim of this programme (Chapter 2), the conditions for the grant application (Chapter 3) and how your proposal will be assessed (Chapter 4). This is the information you need to submit a grant application. Chapter 5 states the obligations for grant recipients in the event you are awarded funding. Chapter 6 contains the contact details and Chapter 7 the annexes.

1.1 Background

The Dutch government has made available substantial funding to support the transition to open science in the Netherlands. The aim of the investment is to make open science the norm.

This call falls within the first work programme of Open Science NL, which covers the years 2024-2025.¹ This work programme addresses a comprehensive set of needs and range of areas relating to open science, and provides a strong basis from which the uptake of open science practices can continue to grow and flourish in the Netherlands. The instruments within this work programme cover the following priority areas:

1. Capacity building,
2. Infrastructure for Open Science,
3. Robust research processes,
4. Evidence base for Open Science,
5. Empowering communities.

The Call for proposals “Replication Studies” falls under the priority area “Robust research processes.”

Replication is an essential part of the scientific method. Scientific studies usually build on previous research. In doing so, it is important to have clarity on which studies confirm each other, and where different outcomes exist. Previous research has shown that the results of many studies cannot be replicated. Differences in outcomes can arise from chance, from undesirable aspects such as publication bias, but also from differences, such as the context in which the study was conducted. Replication research is thus essential to better understand which results are more robust than others.

¹ <https://www.openscience.nl/en/news/open-science-nl-presents-work-programme-for-2024-and-2025>

1.1.1 Changes since the previous Call for proposals

In 2019, the third round of the Replication Studies pilot programme took place. This Call for proposals builds on that round, as well as the advice from the midterm evaluation of the programme. The current round has several major changes compared to the previous round: the Call for proposals is funded by Open Science NL and is open to researchers from all disciplines, including researchers from universities of applied sciences (*hogescholen*). In addition, the types of replication research eligible for funding in this Call for proposals have been expanded to a wider range (see section 2.1). The evaluation criteria have also been adjusted accordingly (see section 4.3).

1.2 Available budget

The available budget for this Call for proposals is €5,200,000.

1.3 Submission deadline

When you submit your application in ISAAC, you will also need to enter some details online. Therefore please start submitting your application at least one day before the deadline of this Call for proposals. Applications that are submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration.

The deadline for submitting full proposals is **Thursday, 6 March 2025**, before 14:00:00 CET.

2 Aim

This chapter describes the aim of the programme and the impact.

2.1 Aim of the programme

By encouraging replication research, Open Science NL aims to contribute to increasing the transparency of research and the quality and completeness of reporting results. Open Science NL follows initiatives such as the Reproducibility Project in psychology, and journals such as *The Journal of Finance* that has launched sections for replications. Open Science NL hopes that by encouraging replication research it can contribute to making replication research more common and to a better understanding of why research does or does not replicate. A second goal is to gain insight into an effective way for the inclusion of replication research in funding programmes, and to gain insight into and reflect on NWO's requirements for research methodology and transparency in its assessments.

For the purpose of this Call for proposals, we distinguish four types of replication research:

1. Replication with existing data (reproduction): re-analysis of the data from the original study, using the same research question;
2. Exact replication: a study with the same research question and method as the original study, but with new data;
3. A less exact replication: a study with the same research question and new data, with necessary adjustments in the study design compared to the original study;
4. Replication with the same research question: a study with the same research question as the original study, but with new data and a different research design.

This Call for proposals only funds research that falls into the first three categories. The aim is to fund applications that propose a replication or reproduction as exact as possible. The goal of the study is to replicate the research in such a way that a statement about the reliability of the original findings can be made on the basis of the results of the replication.

Studies seeking to develop an infrastructure or (new) methodology and new meta-analyses are beyond the scope of this programme.² This Call for proposals aims to fund replication studies, not projects that reflect on replication. NWO endorses the importance of such research, but it is not possible to include it in the current Call for proposals.

Disciplines

The Call for proposals is open to applications for replication research in all NWO and ZonMw disciplines. Replications of psychological laboratory experiments and medicine research are probably the best known forms of replication, but this Call for proposals explicitly targets all research areas. The process of replication does not look the same in every field of science. Within certain disciplines, there is debate about the possibility and feasibility of replications. Open Science NL aims to facilitate replications wherever possible, without preference for or judgement of different research methods.

² Replication of an existing meta-analysis does fall within the scope of Type 1 research.

Cornerstone research

This programme aims to fund replications of so-called cornerstone research: research that has had substantial consequences with respect to theory or policy and for which it is therefore important to assess whether the results on which these consequences are based are reproducible. In their proposal the applicants must argue why the original research that they want to replicate can be regarded as cornerstone research and why it is important to replicate this.

Cornerstone research concerns one or more of the following types of research:

- studies that are frequently cited with far-reaching consequences for subsequent research. This can also include studies with theoretical and/or practical implications for which an intensive post-publication debate has arisen.
- research that plays a major role in policy formation, or studies on the basis of which important policy decisions have been taken; for example, studies that have implications for the organisation and/or funding of healthcare or that play a crucial role or are expected to play a crucial role in a clinical guideline, with implications for the prevention of health problems.
- research that is part of the educational canon: research that is often cited in textbooks for students.
- research that has received a lot of media attention and therefore has a considerable impact on the public debate.
- studies with far-reaching consequences for legislation.

2.2 The impact of replications

Knowledge and insights from scientific research can make an important contribution to developing solutions for the various issues society is facing today and tomorrow. By facilitating greater interaction and alignment between researchers and potential knowledge users, the chance of knowledge utilisation increases, as well as the likelihood of generating societal impact. Societal impact here stands for changes that (partly) result from research-generated knowledge and skills. These changes contribute to the well-being of people, planet and society for this and future generations. Through its policy on impact, NWO promotes the potential contribution that research can make to societal issues by encouraging productive interactions with societal stakeholders, both during the development stage and the subsequent implementation of research. It does so in a manner that is in accordance with the aim of the particular funding instrument. NWO encourages researchers to reflect on the potential desired and undesired impact of their research from a broad perspective.

For replication studies, this primarily means that researchers consider, when preparing their application, what the potential impact of replicating, partially replicating or not replicating the original research could be. Realistic and well considered plans to ensure that the results reach the right people and/or agencies, where appropriate, are taken into account in the assessment.

2.2.1 Tailor-made impact

Depending on the purpose of the funding instrument, NWO chooses a corresponding approach that best supports the opportunity for societal impact. The primary aim of the funding instrument determines the method that NWO will deploy to facilitate knowledge utilisation in various phases of the project (proposal, realisation, project completion) as well as the effort required from the applicant(s) and partner(s).

In this programme, the Impact Outlook approach is applied. Here, researchers can choose which type of impact they want to specifically focus on, while proportional consideration is also given to what can be done for the remaining impact.

NWO offers an e-learning module that can help interested parties via [Online impact workshops | NWO](#). For more information on our policy on impact, please visit the website: [Knowledge utilisation | NWO](#).

3 Conditions for applicants

This chapter contains the conditions that are applicable to your grant application. Firstly it describes who can apply for funding (Section 3.1) and what you can request funding for (Section 3.2). Subsequently, you will find the conditions for preparing and submitting the application (Sections 3.3 and 3.4) and the specific funding conditions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Who can apply

Researchers may submit an application if they have a permanent contract (and therefore a paid position for an indefinite period) or a temporary contract (that covers at least the project duration) at one of the following research organisations:

- universities and universities of applied sciences (UAS) as referred to in Article 1.8 paragraph 1 of the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act and universities listed in the [Policy Rules for Universities located in the Kingdom of the Netherlands](#);
- university medical centres by which is meant academic hospitals as referred to in Article 1.13 paragraph 1 of the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act;
- institutes affiliated to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO;
- Netherlands Cancer Institute;
- the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics in Nijmegen;
- Naturalis Biodiversity Center;
- Advanced Research Centre for NanoLithography (ARCNL);
- Princess Máxima Center.

Persons with a zero-hour employment agreement may not submit a proposal.

It could be the case that the applicant's contract ends due to the applicant reaching retirement age. In that case, the applicant needs to include a statement from their employer in which the research organisation concerned guarantees that the project and all project members for whom funding has been requested will receive adequate supervision for the full duration of the project.

Applicants with a part-time contract should guarantee adequate supervision of the project and all project members for whom funding is requested.

3.1.1 Main and co-applicants

The main applicant submits the proposal via the NWO web application ISAAC. During the assessment process, NWO will communicate with the main applicant. After a proposal has been awarded funding, the main applicant will become the project leader and point of contact for NWO. The knowledge institution of the main applicant is the main beneficiary and will become the official secretary.

Co-applicants have an active role in realising the project. The (sub)project leaders and beneficiary/beneficiaries are jointly responsible for realising the entire project.

3.2 What can be applied for

As described in section 2.1, applications can be submitted in this Call for proposals for three types of replication research. A total maximum of €200,000 can be requested per application, with the following further restrictions per application type:

1. Type 1, a replication with existing data (reproduction): maximum amount to apply for: €100,000;
2. Type 2, an exact replication: maximum amount to apply for: €200,000;
3. Type 3, a less exact replication: maximum amount to apply for: €200,000.

The maximum duration of the proposed project is three years. We would like to point out that the pilot programme has shown that replications are time-consuming, with several stages often taking longer than anticipated.³ The applicant and co-applicant can include costs for personnel, equipment, and knowledge utilisation. The available budget modules (including the maximum amounts) are listed below. Apply only for funding that is vital to realise the project. The rates and an explanation of these budget modules are given in chapter 7.

For all types of replication studies, it is possible to include additions to the replication or reproduction in the proposal, if the comparison with the exact replication or reproduction enriches the proposal. For example, a combination of a Type 1 and Type 2 study is possible, or adding new analyses to a Type 1 study. However, the replication or reproduction study must form the core of the proposal. Such applications combining study types are likewise subject to the maximum application amount of €200,000.

For type 3, the applicant must demonstrate that the proposed deviations in the method are necessary and as minimal as possible. The applicant must also convincingly demonstrate that the proposed method is still sufficiently comparable to that of the original study, thereby maintaining the possibility of drawing an explicit comparison with its results.

Where possible, it is preferable to include multiple replications in a single application. For example, in Type 1 studies, this could include multiple analyses of existing data or re-analysing multiple datasets. For Type 2 and Type 3, multiple studies at different sites could be conducted and combined. Collaboration in consortia, as in *many labs* collaborations for example, is explicitly encouraged, as are collaborations through Study Swap and similar initiatives to meaningfully collaborate with other projects.

3.2.1 Personnel

Funding may be requested for the salary costs of personnel contributing to the project. The amount depends on the type of appointment and the organisation where the personnel is employed.

³ See, for example, the white paper by Derksen, Meirmans et al on experiences with replication studies in the Netherlands: <https://osf.io/preprints/osf/bj8xz>

3.2.1.1 Personnel at a university in the Kingdom of the Netherlands, umc or a research organisation

For personnel working at a university in the Kingdom of the Netherlands, university medical centre (umc) or another research organisation, as referred to in Article 1.1, first paragraph, subparagraphs c to h of the NWO Grant Rules salary costs can be claimed for the following positions: full professor, assistant/associate professor, postdoc, and non-scientific personnel (NWP).

3.2.1.2 Personnel of universities of applied sciences

It is possible to claim salary costs of personnel of universities of applied sciences for the following positions: lector, (*hoofd*)*docent*, data manager, and other similar positions.

3.2.1.3 Students

It is possible to engage students in the project if they are studying at a research organisation as referred to in Section 3.1. You can enter the costs of this as material costs within the project. There is no maximum on the number of students who can participate in the project.

3.2.1.4 Scientific personnel at a research organisation abroad

It is possible to claim salary costs for scientific personnel from foreign research organisations.

3.2.1.5 Personnel costs

You can include the applicant's salary costs.

3.2.2 Material

Funding may be requested for all project-specific material costs.

3.2.3 Knowledge utilisation

Funding can be requested for activities that promote the use of knowledge from the research,⁴ in order to increase the societal impact of the research.

Part of the grant amount can be used for this module. It is not mandatory to make use of this module.

⁴ All activities applied for under this budget module must fit within the definition of "Knowledge Transfer Activities" used by the European Commission in the Framework for State Aid for Research, Development and Innovation (OJEU 2022, C 414).

3.3 Preparing an application

The steps involved in writing your application are:

- download the application form from the NWO web application ISAAC or from the NWO web page (on the grant page of the funding instrument concerned);
- complete the application form;
- save the application form in ISAAC as a PDF file and upload it with any compulsory annexes;
- fill in the requested information online in ISAAC.

Compulsory annex(es):

- budget;
- if applicable: declaration co-funding.

Optional annex(es) only:

- statement appointment;
- declaration material original research;
- declaration cooperation original researcher(s).

The appendix must be drawn up in accordance with the template provided by Open Science NL. Annexes must be uploaded in ISAAC separately from the application. The budget must be submitted in ISAAC as an Excel file. All of the other annexes, except for the budget, must be submitted as PDF files (without encryption). Any annexes other than those stated above are not permitted.

You must write your application in English.

An application can only be submitted via the web application ISAAC. Applications that are not submitted via ISAAC will not be taken into consideration. As the main applicant, you are required to submit the application via your own personal ISAAC account.

It is important to start with your application in ISAAC on time:

- if you do not yet have an ISAAC account, then you should create this on time to prevent any possible registration problems;
- any new research organisations must also be added to ISAAC by NWO;
- you also need to submit other details online.

Applications submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration by Open Science NL.

For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk, see contact (Chapter 6).

Applicants are expected to have informed the research organisation where they work about submitting the application and that the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this Call for proposals.

3.4 Conditions for submission

3.4.1 Formal conditions for submission

Open Science NL will assess your application against all the conditions set out in this Call for proposals, including the conditions listed below. Your application will only be admitted to the assessment procedure if it meets these conditions. After submitting your application, Open Science NL requests you be available to implement any possible administrative corrections so that you can (still) meet the conditions for submission.

These conditions are:

- the main applicant and, if applicable, co-applicant(s) meet the conditions stated in Section 3.1;
- the application complies with the DORA guidelines as described in Section 4.1;
- the application is submitted via the main applicant's ISAAC account;
- the application is received before the deadline;
- the application is written in English;
- the application budget is drawn according to the terms of this Call for proposals (using the format made available which includes the most recent rates);
- the proposed project has a duration of a maximum 3 years;
- all required annexes, after a possible request for additions or changes, have been completed and submitted completely and according to the instructions and in accordance with the terms of this Call for proposals.

3.5 Conditions on granting

The [NWO Grant Rules](#) and the [Agreement on the Payment of Costs for Scientific Research](#) are applicable to all applications.

3.5.1 Compliance with the National Knowledge Security Guidelines

World-class science can benefit from international cooperation. The National Knowledge Security Guidelines (hereafter: the Guidelines) help knowledge institutions to ensure that international cooperation can take place securely. Knowledge security concerns the undesirable transfer of sensitive knowledge and technology that compromises national security; the covert influence of state actors on education and research, which jeopardises academic freedom and social safety; and ethical issues that may arise in cooperation with countries that do not respect fundamental rights.

Applicants are responsible for ensuring that their project complies and will continue to comply with the Guidelines. By submitting an application, the applicant commits to the recommendations stipulated in these Guidelines. In the event of a suspected breach of the Guidelines in an application submitted to NWO for project funding, or in a project funded by NWO, NWO may ask the applicant to provide a risk assessment demonstrating that the recommendations in the Guidelines have been taken into consideration. If the applicant fails to comply with NWO's request, or if the risk assessment is in apparent breach of the Guidelines, this may affect NWO's grant award or decision-making process. NWO may also include further conditions in the award letter if appropriate.

The National Knowledge Security Guidelines can be found on the central government website at: [Home | National Contact Point for Knowledge Security \(loketkennisveiligheid.nl\)](https://www.loketkennisveiligheid.nl).

3.5.2 Data management

NWO expects that research data resulting from NWO-funded projects will be made publicly available, as much as possible, for reuse by other researchers. “As open as possible, as closed as necessary” is the applicable principle in this respect. Researchers, at the very least, are expected to make the data and/or non-numerical results that underlie the conclusions of the published work resulting from the project publicly available at the same time as the work’s publication. Any costs incurred for this can be included in the project budget. Researchers should explain how data emerging from the project will be dealt with based on the data management section in the proposal and the data management plan that is drawn up after funding is awarded.

Data management section

The data management section is part of the proposal. Researchers are asked before the start of the research to consider how the data collected will be ordered and categorised so that this can be made publicly available. Measures will often already need to be taken, both during data generation and as part of analysing the data, to make its subsequent storage and dissemination possible. If it is not possible to make all data from the project publicly available, for example, due to reasons of privacy, ethics or valorisation, then the applicant is obliged to list the reasons for this in the data management section.

The data management section in the proposal is not evaluated and will therefore not be weighed in the decision whether to award funding. However, the committee can issue advice with respect to the data management section.

Transparency: (pre-)registration and publication

Any project funded in this Call for proposals should be pre-registered in a database or registry. In a preregistration, researchers set down in advance a number of aspects of their planned research, such as the plan for analyses and data management. In this way it is possible to show afterwards that the analyses have not been changed during the research, increasing the transparency.

There are several places where research can be preregistered, for example in an Open Ended Registration at the Open Science Forum⁵. In some disciplines, preregistration of research is increasingly common. In other disciplines, this is currently less prevalent. Researchers are requested to act in accordance with the most recent and most progressive developments in the discipline concerned and to demonstrate this in their proposal.⁶

⁵ <https://help.osf.io/article/229-select-a-registration-template>

⁶ This article may be useful in this context, it contains a comprehensive table of information on pre-registration to the Open Science Framework that may also be useful for quantitative researchers less familiar with the phenomenon: L. Haven, T., & Van Grootel, Dr L. (2019). Preregistering qualitative research. *Accountability in Research*, 26(3), 229-244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2019.1580147>

Researchers must describe in their application the content of their preregistration (research protocol, data management plan and data analysis plan) and they should substantiate this. After completion of the study, project leaders ensure that the log of data collection, datasets, description of data analysis (and associated files such as syntaxes and analysis files, if applicable) and all outcomes are uploaded.

In addition to pre-registration, applicants are encouraged to explore the possibilities of submitting and publishing the research protocol to journals (a registered report). Where applicable, applicants are required to state which reporting guidelines they will follow. When animal testing forms part of the proposed research, the ARRIVE guidelines must be adhered to.

3.5.3 Scientific integrity

In accordance with the NWO Grant Rules, the project that Open Science NL funds must be carried out in accordance with the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018). By submitting the proposal, the applicant commits to this code. In the case of a (possible) violation of these standards during a project funded by Open Science NL, the applicant should immediately inform NWO of this and should submit all relevant documents to NWO. More information about the code of conduct and the policy regarding research integrity can be found on the website: [Scientific integrity | NWO](#).

3.5.4 Ethical statement or licence

The applicant is responsible for determining whether an ethical statement or licence is needed for the realisation of the proposed project. The applicant should ensure that this is obtained from the relevant institution or ethics committee on time. The absence or presence of an ethical statement or licence at the time of the application process has no effect on the assessment of the application. If the project is awarded funding, then the grant is issued under the condition that the necessary ethical statement or licence is obtained before the latest start date for the project. The project cannot start until NWO has received a copy of the ethical statement or licence.

3.5.5 Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol ensures an honest and reasonable distribution of benefits emerging from the use of genetic resources (Access and Benefit Sharing; ABS). Researchers who make use of genetic sources from the Netherlands or abroad for their research should familiarise themselves with the Nagoya Protocol ([Home - ABS Focal Point](#)). NWO assumes that researchers will take all necessary actions with respect to the Nagoya Protocol.

3.5.6 Co-funding

All applications are subject to the [Co-funding Scheme](#).

Co-funding is allowed and encouraged when resulting in efficient collaborations with other projects. A distinction is made between co-funding in cash (to be invoiced by the applicant), which serves to cover the budget of the project activities described in the proposal, and co-funding in kind, which may consist of personnel and/or material contributions from the organisations involved. Most importantly, the research must be conducted independently. Interests must be clearly indicated in the conflict of interest section of the application. In case of co-funding, the application must contain a statement that the funding is guaranteed. Co-financing is neither a requirement nor an advantage in the assessment.

Additional definitions:

- co-funding in kind: capitalised personnel and/or material contributions from users;
- co-funding in cash is used to cover part of the total project costs and together with the grant provided by NWO constitutes the required financial resources.

The following principles apply to co-funding:

- NWO is the main funder of an application. Applications for which the co-funding from co-funders exceeds 49% of the total project costs will not be taken into consideration;
- co-funding in cash, is the net amount paid by a co-funder to the applicant. The applicant invoices co-funding in cash and, if applicable, VAT to the co-funder.

Not eligible as co-funding in cash are⁷:

- grant provided by NWO;
- co-funding may not come from parties that according to this Call for proposals can apply for funding to NWO.

Co-funding declaration of participating co-funders

In a co-funding declaration the co-funder expresses financial support for the project and confirms the co-funding promised. Co-funding declarations from co-funders, which are mentioned in the application, are compulsory as attachments when submitting the proposal. The co-funding declaration must be signed by an authorised signatory of the co-funder. NWO provides a compulsory format for the co-funding declaration on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the NWO website and in ISAAC.

If the application is awarded, the co-funder must confirm its contribution(s) in the consortium agreement. This agreement also contains further agreements between the co-funder(s) and the applicant(s) (see Section 5.1.2).

Justification co-funding in cash and in kind

The ratio of co-funding (both in cash and in kind) to the grant provided by NWO in this Call for proposals, applies from submission of an application until the grant is determined. Co-funding in cash affects the grant amount provided by NWO because both NWO's contribution and co-funding in cash are used for the same project-specific costs (unlike co-funding in kind).

⁷ Ineligible co-funding in kind is described in the Co-funding Scheme

One-off indexing due to other applicable rates after submission does not affect the ratio and co-financing requirement for the NWO contribution. For this, NWO assumes the ratio in the application budgets accepted by NWO.

After determination of a project the final grant amount is settled on the basis of the final report, the financial conditions and the co-funding ratio as present in the application budget.

In case of partly provided co-funding in cash (due to unforeseen circumstances, such as bankruptcy) NWO's contribution is based on the original grant award, taking into account the co-funding in cash that was provided and the applicable minimum co-funding requirement, if applicable.

Co-funding in cash in excess of the co-funding requirement affects the applied ratio of co-funding to grant provided by NWO. If a project has co-funding in cash in excess of the co-funding requirement and partial in cash co-funding has been provided at determination, the NWO contribution is never more than the original contribution from the grant award. The ratio of the NWO contribution is then at most the contribution that follows from the co-funding requirement.

At all times NWO must be notified of problems in expected co-funding (in cash and/or in kind). In addition to financial implications for a project, NWO may also require adequate changes to a project as a change request so that research can be continued to the best of its ability.

3.5.7 Additional conditions

Independence from the original researchers

It is important that the applicants were not involved in the research they propose to replicate and have not worked closely with the original researchers in any other context. Applicants must ensure that there is no conflict of interest of any of the team members with the original researchers, or that a bias in carrying out the replication study can be perceived to exist in any other way.

Examples of personal interests that are not allowed in this programme in any case include having co-published with the original researcher(s) (even if this involves other research), or currently collaborating with the original researchers in another project. For this reason, replicating one's own research also falls outside the scope of this programme. For an overview of personal interests, please refer to the examples and categories described in the [NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests](#).

However, it is often desirable to involve the original researcher(s) to some extent in the replication to be carried out. Open Science NL advises applicants to at least inform the original researchers (if possible) about the intended replication and its outcomes.

Contact with the original applicants is also often necessary to request relevant information and data. Applicants need to be in possession of the information about the research they propose to replicate that is necessary to carry out the replication. The original publication generally does not contain sufficient information for this. The applicants have to convince the assessment committee that they have the necessary information, or will have access to this if the project is funded. If agreements have been made with the original researcher(s) regarding access to archives, data, protocols and the like, a confirmation of those agreements by the original researchers should be included in the application as an appendix.

The value and impact of a replication can be enhanced by involving the original researcher(s) in a replication that is nevertheless conducted independently. Discussing the design of the replication in advance with the original researcher(s) can improve the implementation. Some type of collaboration after completion of the study, for example, to reflect on any differences in outcomes in constructive and critical dialogue, is encouraged. Applicants must state in their application whether the original researchers have been informed or approached about the proposal. If the original researchers are involved in the proposed research in this form, a confirmation thereof by the original researchers should also be included as an appendix in the application. The application should make clear that the original investigators have no active investigator role in the replication study.

Data quality accountability

In the case of a Type 2 or Type 3 study, the application should demonstrate that the replication is carried out based on data of sufficient scope and quality to allow conclusions to be drawn. For example, when using written materials or databases, it is important that the application convincingly shows that the source corpus consulted is qualitatively comparable to or better than the corpus in the original study, and has the quality required for replication. When replicating quantitative empirical research involving a sample, a justification for the sample size should be included in the application.⁸ Applicants must explicitly discuss in their application how they will substantiate their conclusions about whether or not the study was successfully replicated.

3.5.8 Sharing results

Open Science NL finds it important that the results of all projects are shared, including projects that do not produce the anticipated results. A public summary of all funded projects will be published online. At the end of each project, Open Science NL will request a short report that will also be published online.

⁸ To estimate the required sample size, traditional power analysis is often used, basing the expected effect size on previous literature. This method is problematic. There is compelling evidence that published effects are often overestimated due to publication bias and outcome reporting bias (where significant effects are more likely to be published than non-significant effects) and (too) flexible data analyses. Using an overestimated effect as an input to a power analysis will underestimate the sample size needed for replication. Possible ways to get around this problem are the following: 1. Focus on the precision of effect size estimation. Calculate the number of observations needed to estimate an effect with a margin of X. 2. Calculate the sample size needed for the desired power to find the smallest, still relevant effect or to demonstrate statistical equivalence, given the smallest, still relevant effect size.

4 Assessment procedure

This chapter first describes the assessment according to the DORA principles (Section 4.1) and the course of the assessment procedure (Section 4.2). Second, it states the criteria that the assessment committee will use to assess your application (Section 4.3).

The NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests applies to all persons and NWO employees involved in the assessment and/or decision-making process ([Code for Dealing with Personal Interests | NWO](#)).

NWO strives to achieve an inclusive culture where there is no place for conscious or unconscious barriers due to cultural, ethnic or religious background, gender, sexual orientation, health or age ([Diversity and inclusion | NWO](#)). NWO actively encourages members of an assessment committee to be aware of implicit associations and to try to minimise these. NWO will provide them with information about concrete ways of improving the assessment of an application.

4.1 The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)

NWO is a signatory to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). DORA is a worldwide initiative that aims to improve the way research and researchers are assessed. DORA contains recommendations for research funders, research institutions, scientific journals and other parties.

DORA aims to reduce the uncritical use of bibliometric indicators and obviate unconscious bias in the assessment of research and researchers. DORA's overarching philosophy is that research should be evaluated on its own merits rather than based on surrogate measures, such as the journal in which the research is published.

When assessing the scientific track record of applicants, NWO makes use of a broad definition of scientific output.

NWO requests committee members not to rely on indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor or the h-index when assessing applications. Applicants are not allowed to mention these in their applications. You are, however, allowed to list other scientific products besides publications, such as datasets, patents, software and code, et cetera.

For more information on how NWO is implementing the principles of DORA, see [DORA | NWO](#).

4.2 Procedure

The application procedure consists of the following steps:

- submission of the proposal;
- admissibility check of the proposal;
- interview selection:
 - assessment criteria A and B, potentially assessment criteria 1 to 3 (see Section 4.2.3 for details);
 - initial advice from the assessment committee;

- possibility to submit a request for correction of a factual inaccuracy in the negative initial advice;
- decision-making interview selection by Open Science NL;
- assessment of the proposal based on all criteria:
 - pre-advice assessment committee;
 - interview;
 - assessment committee meeting;
- decision-making by the Steering Board of Open Science NL.

An external, independent assessment committee will be assigned for this Call for proposals, consisting of representatives from science with knowledge of the field. The task of the assessment committee is to assess the applications and the relevant documents that are submitted, in conjunction with each other and with regard to both the respective merits of each application and the assessment criteria outlined in this Call for proposals. The composition of the committee may be adjusted for the interview phase of the assessment.

Due to the expertise present in the assessment committee, Open Science NL has decided with regard to the assessment of these applications to exercise the option outlined in Article 2.2.4, paragraph 2, of the NWO Grant Rules, to assess all applications without involving referees.

Keep in mind when writing your application that the committee is broad in its composition and may not include an expert from your own discipline. The application should therefore also be accessible to committee members from other disciplines.

4.2.1 Submission of a proposal

For the submission of the proposal, a standard form is available on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the NWO website. When you write your proposal, you must adhere to the questions stated on this form and the procedure given in the explanatory notes. You must also adhere to the conditions for the maximum number of words and pages.

Your complete application form must have been received before the deadline via ISAAC (see Section 1.3). After this deadline, you can no longer submit a proposal. After submitting the proposal, the main applicant will receive a confirmation of receipt.

4.2.2 Admissibility of the proposal

As soon as possible after you have submitted your proposal, you will hear from NWO whether or not your proposal will be taken into consideration. NWO will determine this based on several administrative-technical criteria (see the formal conditions for submission, Section 3.4). NWO can only take your proposal into consideration if it meets these conditions.

Please bear in mind that within two weeks after the submission deadline, NWO may approach you with any possible administrative corrections that need to be made so that your proposal can (still) meet the conditions for submission. You will be given one opportunity to make the corrections, and you will be given five working days to do this.

4.2.3 Interview selection

In the interview selection phase, all applications considered will be assessed by the assessment committee on the basis of the following two criteria (see section 4.3.1 for a more detailed description):

- A. Alignment with the aim of the Call for proposals;
- B. Independence from the original researchers.

Only applications that meet both criteria will be considered for the interview phase.

If the total requested budget of the applications that meet criteria A and B is at least twice the total available budget (as specified in section 1.2), an additional selection round will take place. For this additional selection, the assessment committee will assess the applications that meet criteria A and B using part of the assessment criteria applicable in the interview phase (see section 4.3.2 for a more detailed description of these criteria), namely:

1. Relationship to the original study;
2. Availability of the required data;
3. Quality of the replication study.

These three criteria carry equal weight in the assessment. The assessment committee makes a ranking based on which proposals have the most chance of being awarded funding, taking into account the representativeness of the selected applications by NWO-domain compared to the submitted applications that received at least a score of 3.4 on these three criteria.⁹ For this purpose, applicants are asked to indicate in their application under which domain their research falls.

Applicants will be informed if their application is assessed negatively on criteria A and/or B. In case of the additional selection based on criteria 1 to 3, the applicants with the least chance will be informed that the committee does not intend to select their proposals for interview. If the applicant is of the opinion that the provisional assessment contains a factual error, the applicant will subsequently be given five working days to submit a request for correction of that error, using the format provided. This response is not meant to include additional, new information about the proposal, nor is it meant as a way to ask questions to the committee. Taking this information into account, the assessment committee will consider whether there is cause to revise the provisional assessment. After this consideration, the assessment committee formulates its definitive advice to Open Science NL to reject the least promising applications and applications that do not meet criteria A and/or B. The remaining applications will proceed to the interview phase.

Applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be assessed using the criteria below. Depending on the stage of the assessment procedure, different criteria apply (see sections 4.2.3 and 4.2.4).

⁹ Should the numbers of applications submitted in underlying disciplines warrant it, the disciplinary distribution within domains may also be taken into account.

4.2.4 Pre-advice assessment committee

After this, your proposal will be submitted for comments to several members of the assessment committee (the pre-advisers). The pre-advisers will provide a written substantive and reasoned response to the proposal. They will formulate these comments based on the substantive assessment criteria (see Section 4.3.2) and will give the proposal a numerical score per assessment criterion. For this, the NWO score table will be used (on a scale of 1 to 9, where “1” is excellent and “9” unsatisfactory).

4.2.5 Interview

During the interview, the assessment committee will have the opportunity to pose questions. During the interview, the applicant will be able to respond to these in the discussion with the committee. In this manner, the principle of having a hearing and an opportunity for rebuttal is applied. The interview is an important part of the assessment procedure and can lead to an adjustment of both the assessment and the score of the proposal.

4.2.6 Meeting of the assessment committee

The committee will make its own assessment based on the available material. Although the pre-advises will ‘guide’ the final assessment to a large extent, it will not be blindly accepted without question by the committee. The committee will consider and compare the arguments of the pre-advisers (also amongst each other) and examine whether the rebuttal contains a well-formulated response to the critical comments from the pre-advises.

Following the discussion, the committee draws up a written recommendation addressed to Steering Group Open Science NL about the quality and ranking of the proposals. This recommendation is based on the assessment criteria. The proposal must receive an overall qualification of at least “very good” to be eligible for funding. The proposal must also receive at least the qualification “good” for each of the individual assessment criteria.

For more information about the qualifications, see [Applying for funding, how does it work? | NWO](#).

If, after the discussion of the proposals, two or more of the proposals cannot be distinguished from each other based on their weighted total score, then this will result in an ex aequo situation (see Section 4.2.7).

4.2.7 Ex aequo

NWO understands ex aequo to be a situation in which two or more proposals based on their weighted score cannot be distinguished from each other. An ex aequo situation is relevant with respect to the borders of the available budget or the selection borders. The existence of an ex aequo situation is determined as follows. The starting point in this process is the ranking drawn up by the assessment committee, with the final scores rounded down to two decimal points. The reference score here is the score of the lowest-ranked proposal within the borders of the available budget or the selection borders. All proposals with a score that is within 0.05 or less of the reference score will be considered. In this way, the proposals that are equal within a score of 0.1 will be selected. If an ex aequo situation occurs at the borders of the available budget or the selection borders, then, in order to help increase the number of women working in the scientific field, the proposal from a female applicant will end as the highest. If the ex aequo situation is not resolved via this procedure, then the proposal with the highest score for criterion 1, relation to the original study, will be ranked highest. If the proposals subsequently still remain tied, then the assessment committee, with the help of an (anonymous) majority vote, will determine the ranking (in accordance with Article 2.2.6, paragraph 5 of the NWO Grant Rules). If this vote also fails to provide a resolution, or if it is deemed to be undesirable to vote, then the ex aequo situation will be sent onto the decision-making body.

4.2.8 Decision-making

Finally, the Steering Group Open Science NL will assess the procedure followed as well as the advice from the assessment committee. They will subsequently determine the final qualifications and make a decision over awarding or rejecting the proposals.

4.2.9 Timetable

Below, you will find the timetable for this Call for proposals. During the current procedure, NWO might find it necessary to make further changes to the timetable for this Call for proposals. You will be informed about this in time.

Proposals	
Thursday 6 March 2025, 14:00 CET	Deadline proposals
March – May 2025	Interview selection by the assessment committee
End of May 2025	Initial advice interview selection
June/July 2025	Decision Steering Group Open Science NL regarding interview selection
September 2025	Pre-advice assessment committee
September/October 2025	Interviews and assessment committee meeting
December 2025	Decision Steering Group Open Science NL

4.3 Criteria

The applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be assessed on the basis of the criteria below. Depending on the phase of the assessment procedure, different criteria apply (see Section 4.2.3 and 4.2.4).

4.3.1 Assessment criteria interview selection

During the interview selection process, applications will be assessed to see if they meet both of the following criteria:

- A. Alignment with the aim of the Call for proposals
 - Is the submitted proposal a Type 1, Type 2 or Type 3 study as defined in section 2.1?
- B. Independence from the original researchers
 - Will the replication study be carried out independently from and without conflict of interest with the original researchers (see section 3.5.7)?
 - If the original researchers play a role in the proposed research: is the description clear as to what the cooperation with the original researchers will consist of? Is it clear that the original researchers will not have an active researcher role in the proposed research? If they are involved in the design and/or interpretation of the results, is this done in such a way that the independence of the replication is maintained?

The starting point for criterion B is that there is no history of cooperation with the original researchers in the context of the studies that will be replicated. As the complete absence of any previous cooperation is not realistic in some fields, section 3.5.7 provides further information on forms of involvement that are excluded from this programme in all cases.

4.3.2 Assessment criteria interview phase

In the interview phase, applications will be substantively assessed according to the following criteria:

1. Relation to the original study (20%);
 2. Availability of the required data (20%);
 3. Quality of the replication study (20%);
 4. Registration, publication and dissemination (20%);
 5. Applicants and budget (20%).
1. Relation to the original study
 - a. To what extent can the original study be considered cornerstone research as defined in section 2.1? Do the applicants provide convincing arguments why precisely this study should be repeated?
 - b. The impact of replication:
 - i. To what extent is the potential and relevance of the proposed research to the main research area, related areas and the broader scientific field convincing?
 - ii. To what extent is the potential and relevance of the proposed plan to achieve societal impact convincing?
 - c. Is the type of study chosen (1, 2 or 3) the most appropriate form of replication for this study? Is there a convincing case to argue that it is not a Type 4 replication study? If the design of the replication differs from the original study (Type 3), have the applicants

convincingly demonstrated that these modifications are necessary, and have they justified why a Type 1 or Type 2 study is not possible or appropriate?

2. Availability of the required data
 - a. Do the researchers have access to the relevant data from the original study needed to conduct the replication study (e.g.: required data, original codings, and the analysis plan for Type 1 or the study design for Type 2 or Type 3 studies)? If these data are still to be obtained from the original researchers, have clear agreements been made with them about making them available (see the mandatory annex 'Declaration of material original study' in this case)?
 - b. If the information mentioned under 2a. is not available, what are the consequences of this for the feasibility of the replication?
 - c. If the original researchers will provide access to information that is essential for the replication study and/or will be involved in reflecting on the results, is a convincing confirmation of this included in the application, in which the original researcher explicitly states the role described by the applicants?

3. Quality of the replication study
 - a. Are the data that will be used for the proposed research of sufficient quality for this study? If there is quantitative empirical research involving a sample: does a sample size justification and/or power analysis show that the sample is large enough? See the explanation in Section 3.5.7.
 - b. To what extent is the replication study work plan clear, feasible and effective?
 - c. Does the proposed work plan enable the researchers to draw a clear conclusion on the replicability of the original research?

4. Registration, publication and dissemination
 - a. Is there a clear plan for pre-registration of the study, and the recording of data, data analysis, protocols and other relevant information about the study? Is this in line with the latest and most progressive developments in the discipline?
 - b. To what extent is the plan for publication and dissemination of the results concrete, appropriate and realistic for the discipline in question? Does the plan for publication and dissemination miss any opportunities?

5. Applicants and budget
 - a. Quality of applicants. To what extent are the researchers capable of carrying out the proposed research? Do the researchers possess the right subject-specific and methodological knowledge and experience required for the proposed research?
 - b. Is the requested budget reasonable for the realisation of the proposed research (value for money)?

Scores will be assigned to the criteria (and in the case of the interview selection, a subset of the criteria). In assessing the proposals in phase 2, a 9-point scale will be used, on which 1 represents the highest/best score, and 9 the lowest/worst.

On the basis of the scores and overall standardised mean score will be calculated. This overall average score constitutes the final score. The final score will determine the position in the ranking.

5 Obligations for grant recipients

This chapter details the various obligations that - in addition to the conditions stated in Section 3.5 - apply after funds have been awarded.

5.1 Additional terms and conditions

5.1.1 Data management

After a proposal has been awarded funding, the researcher should elaborate the data management section into a data management plan. For this, applicants can make use of the advice from the referees and committee. The applicant must describe in the plan whether existing data will be used, or whether new data will be collected or generated, and how this data will be made FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. Before submission, the data management plan should be checked by a data steward or similar officer of the research organisation where the project will be realised. The plan must be submitted to NWO through ISAAC no later than four months after the application is awarded. NWO will check the plan as quickly as possible. Approval of the data management plan by NWO is a condition for disbursement of the funding. The plan can be adjusted during the research.

More information about the data management protocol of NWO can be found at: [Research data management | NWO](#).

5.1.2 Intellectual property and consortium agreement

With respect to intellectual property (IP), the NWO IP policy applies. This can be found in Chapter 4 of the NWO Grant Rules.

Applicants must carry out a project funded by NWO during the time that they work for the research organisation. If an applicant or a researcher funded by NWO is appointed by more than one employer, then the other employer should relinquish any possible IP rights that emerge from the project of the applicant.

After a proposal has been awarded funding, the conclusion of a consortium agreement is one of the conditions for starting the project. In this agreement, arrangements are made about intellectual property and publication, knowledge transfer, confidentiality, co-financing payments, progress reports, and final reports. Uploading in ISAAC is required before the project can start.

The model agreement that NWO makes available must be used and can be found on the funding page of this Call for proposals. This model agreement has been drawn up in accordance with the NWO Grant Rules.

5.1.3 Open Access

As a signatory to the Berlin Declaration (2003) and a member of cOAlition S (2018), NWO is committed to making the results of the research it funds openly accessible via the internet (Open Access). By doing this, NWO gives substance to the ambitions of the Dutch government to make all publicly funded research available in Open Access form. Scientific publications arising from projects awarded on the basis of this Call for proposals must therefore be made available in Open Access form in accordance with the Open Access Policy.

Scientific articles

Scientific articles must be made available in Open Access form immediately at the time of publication (without embargo) via one of the following routes:

- publication in a fully Open Access journal or platform registered in the DOAJ;
- publication in a subscription journal and the immediate deposition of at least the author accepted manuscript of the article in an Open Access repository registered in Open DOAR;
- publication in a journal for which a transformative Open Access agreement exists between UNL and a publisher. For further information, see [Home | Open access](#).

Books

Different requirements apply to scholarly books, book chapters and edited collections. See the Open Access Policy Framework at [Open Science | NWO](#).

CC BY licence

To ensure the widest possible dissemination of publications, at least a Creative Commons (CC BY) licence must be applied. Alternatively – in case of substantial interest – the author may request to publish under a CC BY-ND licence. For books, book chapters and collected volumes, all CC BY licence options is allowed.

Costs

Costs for publication in fully Open Access journals can be budgeted in the application using the budget module for “material costs”. Costs for publications in hybrid journals are not eligible for reimbursement by NWO. For Open Access books, a separate NWO Open Access Books Fund is available.

For more detailed information about NWO’s Open Access policy, see [Open Science | NWO](#).

6 Contact and other information

6.1 Contact

6.1.1 Specific questions

For specific questions about this Call for proposals, please contact:

Amy de Bruïne, via replicatiestudies@nwo.nl

6.1.2 Technical questions about the web application ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Please read the manual first before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk can be contacted from Monday to Friday between 10:00 and 17:00 hours on +31 (0)70 34 40 600. However, you can also submit your question by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will then receive an answer within two working days.

6.2 Other information

The whole text of this Call for proposals has been published in both Dutch and English. The Dutch version is deemed authentic. For legal interpretation the text of the Dutch version will be decisive.

NWO processes data from applicants received in the context of this Call for proposals in accordance with the NWO Privacy Statement, [Privacy Statement | NWO](#).

NWO might approach applicants for an evaluation of the procedure and/or research programme.

7 Annexes

7.1 Budget modules and rates

7.1.1 Personnel

Postdoc

A postdoc is appointed to a university in the Kingdom of the Netherlands, umc or research organisation as listed in Section 3.1.

Use the rates of a senior academic employee in the salary tables of UNL, and the rates of a postdoc at an umc in the salary tables of NFU.

It is not possible to apply for funding for a postdoc who started the project to be funded before the grant is awarded.

Only a postdoc position with an appointment of at least 12 months for 0.5 fte qualifies as an appointment for which a one-off personal bench fee of €5,000 is available to boost the scientific career.

Non-scientific personnel

Funding may be requested for non-scientific personnel (NWP) needed to execute the project. The use of NWP must be described in the proposal.

The duration of the appointment cannot be longer than the duration of the project funded by NWO.

Rates will be determined using the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT-Manual Dutch Government rates], Table 2.2 average total labour costs by salary scale, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for university of applied sciences and NCB Naturalis and Table 2.1 average direct labour costs, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for universities, university medical centres and KNAW and NWO institutes. The salary scale of the requested position determines the rate from the HOT table.

(Hoofd)docenten, lectors and professors

Funding can be requested for salary costs of (senior) lectors and professors at universities, university medical centres, and universities of applied sciences. The use of (senior) lectors and professors must be described in the application. Supervision for a PhD student or postdoc is not eligible for funding. The duration of the appointment should not exceed the duration of the NWO-funded project.

Rates will be determined using the Handleiding Overheidstarieven [HOT-Manual Dutch Government rates], Table 2.2 average total labour costs by salary scale, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for university of applied sciences and NCB Naturalis and Table 2.1 average direct labour costs, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for universities, university medical centres and KNAW and NWO institutes. The salary scale of the requested position determines the rate from the HOT table. For professors, scale 17 applies.

Scientific personnel at a research organisation abroad

Funding may be requested for personnel costs of a foreign research organisation contributing to the project. The foreign research organisation must meet the definition of research organisation in Article 5.1(p) of the NWO Grant Rules.

Substantiate convincingly how the researcher of the foreign research organisation contributes specific expertise to the project which is not available in the Netherlands at the level required for the project. The assessment committee assesses this substantiation as part of criterion 5 'Applicants and budget'. This substantiation is not necessary when NWO has concluded a bilateral agreement on *Money Follows Cooperation* with the national research financier of the country where the foreign research organisation is located. The [NWO website](#) lists the research funders with which NWO has such an agreement. NWO does not award grants to co-applicants abroad who are subject to applicable sanction legislation.

The main applicant receives the grant and is responsible for transferring grant funds to the co-applicant's foreign research organisation and for accounting for the use of the foreign part of the grant. The exchange rate risk lies with the applicant. Benefits or expenses due to exchange rates are not eligible.

Use UNL rates adjusted for [country correction coefficients](#). These rates are maximums. No one-off personal bench fee is available.

If more than €125,000 per organisation is requested within this budget module, an audit certificate is required with the final financial statement.

Students

Students may be engaged in research. If the students contribute as part of their curriculum, the rate according to the usual internship fee of the university or universities of applied sciences applies.

If students contribute as a secondary job alongside their studies as student assistants, the rate according to HOT table 2 scale 1 applies.

7.1.2 Material

Funding may be requested for all project-specific costs relating to, among others, consumables, purchase of services, materials, small instruments, access to (inter)national facilities, software and research resources that have no economic value after use. Travel and accommodation costs (national and international) for all people working on the project incl. foreign guest researchers, costs for the organisation of (international) workshops and symposia, costs for data management, publications, and costs in the context of citizen science also fall under this module.

Travel expenses (national and international) will only be reimbursed on the basis of second class/economy class fares. For publications, the provisions in Section 5.1.3 Open access apply. Costs for an audit statement can only be claimed for organisations that are not subject to OCW's education audit protocol for a maximum of €5,000 per audit statement.

It is not permitted to include costs for:

- organisational infrastructure and overhead, including a fully functioning workplace, accommodation, office automation, personnel administration, commuting expenses, training, facilities, HR advice and business care, documentary information provision and home office allowance;
- the use and maintenance of in-house developed scientific infrastructure;
- regular teaching activities;
- members of the guidance committee/user committee.

7.1.3 Knowledge utilisation

The budget requested should be adequately specified in the proposal. To determine the rates, use the provisions of Personnel and Material.

It is possible to use part of the grant amount for this module. There is no obligation to use this module. Examples of possible costs, but not limited to, are the creation of a teaching curriculum, a feasibility study on application possibilities, and costs for filing a patent application or engaging a business developer.

7.2 Indexing

The rate at the time of the decision date applies. NWO will, if necessary, apply a one-off indexation of personnel costs when awarding the grant. The date on which the rates take effect is used for this purpose. If the date of publication of the fees is later than the effective date, the date of publication is used. The tariffs of the Universities of the Netherlands (UNL) usually take effect on 1 July, of the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU) on 1 August and of the Government Tariffs Manual (HOT) on 1 January.

The on-off indexation does not affect the grant ceiling and the maximum grant amount to be applied for. The grant ceiling and maximum requestable grant amount remain unchanged during the assessment procedure. If awarded, one-off indexation will be applied to the grant amount.

If co-funding is required or permitted, the one-off indexation does not affect the requirements for own contributions and co-funding, nor the IP rights that may result from the co-funding.

Publication: January 2025

Dutch Research Council

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